

Polarographic Study of Cinchomeric Acid in various Aquo-organic Mixtures

P. YADAGIRI SWAMY, G. VEERABHADRAM and K. S. SASTRY*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

Manuscript received 30 April 1985, revised 4 March 1986, accepted 2 April 1986

The polarographic reduction of cinchomeric acid has been studied in 1 : 1 aquo-organic mixtures of various organic solvents of methanol, ethanol, n-propanol, dioxane, dimethyl formamide, dimethyl sulphoxide and ethylene glycol in buffered and unbuffered solutions. The limiting current is found to decrease, while the half-wave potential is found to shift to more negative values in the presence of organic solvent. Similar behaviour is also observed with the increase in the percentage of ethanol. The limiting current is diffusion-controlled and the reduction process is found to be irreversible. The kinetic parameters have been deduced using Meites-Israel method.

THE electrochemical reduction of pyridine carboxylic acids¹⁻⁴ was a subject of many investigations. The polarographic reduction of pyridine dicarboxylic acids was attempted by Tissier and Agoutin⁵. They studied the variations of diffusion current and half-wave potential with pH, and deduced the values for the three equilibrium constants of cinchomeric acid. Campanella and Chiacchierini⁶ made polarographic studies of dipicolinic acid, and interpreted the data on the basis of equilibria among the six species in which the acid could exist in aqueous solution. Brown *et al.*⁷ investigated the electrochemical reduction of picolinic and dipicolinic acids and their aldehydes at a mercury pool cathode to hydroxymethylpyridines.

In the present work, the polarographic study of cinchomeric acid has been conducted in various aquo-organic mixtures to understand the effect of medium on the diffusion current, half-wave potential and kinetics. Aquo-organic mixtures of (1 : 1) methanol, ethanol, n-propanol, dioxane, dimethyl formamide, dimethyl sulphoxide and ethylene glycol and various percentages of ethanol with water in buffered and unbuffered solutions were used for this purpose.

Experimental

Cinchomeric acid was obtained from SIGMA (U.S.A.). All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The organic solvents were used after necessary purifications as given in literature⁸⁻¹⁰. The concentration of cinchomeric acid was 1mM. The buffer solution of pH 1.34 was obtained by

mixing hydrochloric acid and sodium acetate. The buffer solution of pH 3.01 was obtained for Britton-Robinson¹¹ modified universal buffer solutions. Potassium chloride was used as a supporting electrolyte. The pH values of the solutions were checked with a Elico LI-120 digital pH meter. Triton-x-100 (5 × 10⁻⁴%) was used as a maximum suppressor. The polarograph was a CLO 2A manual polarograph with Toshniwal a PL50 polyflex galvanometer. The viscosity of the solution was measured with an Ostwald's viscometer, and the values obtained are comparable with the reported values.

Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solution to flush out O₂ before each polarogram was taken. The capillary delivered 2.835 mg of mercury per sec at a corrected mercury column height of 17.08 cm. The drop time was 3.8 sec (in distilled water, open circuit). The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The measurements were made at a constant temperature of 30 ± 0.1° maintained with a thermostat.

Results and Discussion

The polarographic behaviour of 1mM of cinchomeric acid in the presence of 1 : 1 aquo-organic mixtures of various organic solvents, viz. methanol, ethanol, n-propanol, dioxane, dimethyl formamide, dimethyl sulphoxide and ethylene glycol has been studied both in buffered and unbuffered solutions (at pH 1.34 and 3.01). In all these cases a single well defined cathodic wave is obtained. The limiting current is found to decrease with the increase in

pH of buffer solution, while the half-wave potential shifted to more negative values. This indicates that the electrode reaction is governed by the rate of proton transfer¹³, which becomes slower at higher pH values. A shift of the half-wave potential towards more negative value indicates that the electrodic reaction is increasingly difficult at higher pH values. The polarograms of cinchomeric acid in the presence of various organic solvents at pH 1.34 are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Polarograms of cinchomeric acid at a pH of 1.34 in aquoorganic mixtures of various organic solvents: (A) methanol; (B) dioxane; (C) ethanol; (D) dimethyl formamide; (E) n-propanol; (F) dimethyl sulphoxide; (G) ethylene glycol.

There is a marked decrease in the value of diffusion current with the addition of the organic solvent, and the extent of decrease depends on the nature of the organic solvent. This decrease in the diffusion current may be attributed to the increase in the viscosity of the solution. The $i_d \eta^{1/2}$ values are given in Table 1. The half-wave potential is shifted to more negative value in the presence of organic solvents (Table 1). The diffusion-controlled nature of the polarographic wave is evident from the linearity of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ plots. The conventional log plots, i.e. $-E_{1/2}$ vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$ are straight lines but their slopes are more than the theoretically expected values for a reversible wave. This indicates the irreversible nature of the electrodic reaction.

The $k_{f,h}^0$ (formal heterogeneous rate constant) values are calculated using the method of Meites and Israel¹³ and are shown in Table 1. The diffusion coefficient value necessary for the calculation of $k_{f,h}^0$ is deduced by the procedure given in the literature¹³. The values of $k_{f,h}^0$ are found to decrease in the presence of organic solvents and with the increase in the chain length of the alcohol. The deduced αn (α -transfer coefficient, n = number of electrons involved in the rate determining step) values are shown in Table 1, which are comparable to the values deduced in the absence of organic solvents. This shows that the mechanism of electrochemical reaction is similar even in the presence of organic solvents, although a marked shift in diffusion current and $E_{1/2}$ is observed.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIOUS AQUOORGANIC MIXTURES (1 : 1) ON THE POLAROGRAPHIC WAVE OF 1 mM OF CINCHOMERIC ACID

Solvent	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$i_d \eta^{1/2}$ pH = 1.34	r A	αn	$k_{f,h}^0$ $cm\ s^{-1}$
Water	11.98	0.647	10.66	10.92	1.161	1.56×10^{-11}
Methanol	9.24	0.643	10.70	10.91	1.096	3.83×10^{-11}
Ethanol	8.43	0.646	11.71	9.12	1.093	2.91×10^{-11}
n-Propanol	7.49	0.657	10.94	10.40	1.078	2.16×10^{-11}
Dioxane	8.80	0.635	11.50	9.45	1.154	1.94×10^{-11}
Dimethyl formamide	7.99	0.728	11.35	9.69	1.162	0.26×10^{-11}
Dimethyl sulphoxide	6.99	0.651	11.25	9.84	1.085	2.30×10^{-11}
Ethylene glycol	6.50	0.640	10.79	10.73	1.072	4.32×10^{-11}
pH = 3.01						
Water	10.64	0.812	9.52	13.82	1.020	9.98×10^{-14}
Methanol	8.24	0.842	9.56	13.72	0.993	9.73×10^{-14}
Ethanol	7.49	0.850	10.41	11.68	0.977	8.71×10^{-14}
n-Propanol	6.61	0.863	9.65	13.45	0.956	8.22×10^{-14}
Dioxane	7.86	0.840	10.30	11.86	1.001	7.95×10^{-14}
Dimethyl formamide	7.05	0.908	10.01	12.52	0.962	1.39×10^{-14}
Dimethyl sulphoxide	6.18	0.882	9.95	12.65	0.935	6.21×10^{-14}
Ethylene glycol	5.75	0.844	9.43	13.76	0.940	7.84×10^{-14}
Unbuffered media						
Water	8.34	0.836	7.68	24.08	1.121	1.92×10^{-14}
Methanol	6.37	0.830	7.39	23.08	1.098	1.66×10^{-14}
Ethanol	5.49	0.835	7.63	21.56	1.078	1.52×10^{-14}
n-Propanol	4.74	0.843	6.87	26.01	1.062	1.47×10^{-14}
Dioxane	5.92	0.818	7.76	20.98	1.113	1.46×10^{-14}
Dimethyl formamide	5.12	0.871	7.27	23.62	1.057	0.56×10^{-14}
Dimethyl sulphoxide	4.24	0.827	6.83	26.72	1.046	3.72×10^{-14}
Ethylene glycol	3.74	0.829	6.21	32.51	1.035	4.23×10^{-14}

The effect of change of concentration of ethanol on the polarographic reduction of cinchomeronic acid has been studied at pH 3.01. Various percentages of ethanol with water have been used for this purpose. The limiting current is found to decrease with increase in the alcohol content of the medium as shown in Fig. 2 without the actual process being altered essentially. This decrease

Fig. 2. Plots of (a) i_d and (b) $i_d \eta^{1/2}$ vs volume percentage of ethanol for the polarographic reduction of cinchomeronic acid at pH 3.01.

may be attributed to the decrease in the effective diffusion coefficient which may result either from an increase in the viscosity of the solution or a change in the size of the solvated species¹⁴. Since in different cases these two effects may tend either to reinforce or compensate each other, a quantitative estimation of the individual influences may be difficult.

The plots of $i_d \eta^{1/2}$ vs ethanol concentration are shown in Fig. 2. The increase in the volume of the reducible species is most probably due to a higher tendency of these species to be solvated by the ethanol molecules than water¹⁵. The change in current should accordingly be the resultant effect of the increase in viscosity and the molecular volume which in turn lowers the diffusion coefficient. The equations of Ilkovic¹⁶ and Stokes-Einstein¹⁷ can be used to order to get the following form¹⁵.

$$i_d = 708 n \text{ cm}^{2/3} t^{1/6} \left(\frac{3.38 \times 10^{-5}}{(4/3 \pi r^3 N)} \right)^{1/2} \eta^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where, i_d = diffusion current (μA), n = number of electrons involved in the reduction process, c = concentration of the depolariser (mM), r = radius of the diffusing particle (cm), m = flow

rate (mg s^{-1}), N = Avagadro number. Equation (1) can be simplified as

$$r = k^3 / i_d^2 \eta, \quad (2)$$

where, $k = (3.53 n \text{ cm}^{2/3} t^{1/6}) 10^{-4}$. The data of Table 2 show that the radius of the reduced species increases with increase in the ethanol content of the medium.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ETHANOL CONCENTRATION ON THE POLAROGRAPHIC WAVE OF 1 mM OF CINCHOMERONIC ACID

Ethanol %	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$i_d \eta^{1/2}$	r A	αn_a	$k^{\circ} r, h$ cm s^{-1}
10	13.98	0.841	14.68	5.82	0.988	12.42
25	11.42	0.846	14.39	5.98	0.985	10.74
50	9.68	0.859	13.46	6.92	0.972	8.85
60	9.24	0.867	12.66	7.77	0.966	7.92
75	8.91	0.880	11.58	9.33	0.954	5.92

The half-wave potential is found to shift to more negative values with increase in the percentage of ethanol as shown in Table 2 and Fig. 3. This can be attributed to several factors, namely, dielectric

Fig. 3. Plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs (A) volume percentage of ethanol, and (B) reciprocal dielectric constant, for the polarographic reduction of cinchomeronic acid at pH 3.01.

constant (ϵ), solvation of ions, and absorption of organic solvent at the electrode surface. The variation of $E_{1/2}$ with ϵ is given by the Takahashi relation¹⁸,

$$E_{1/2(S)} = E_{1/2(W)} - K \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_{(W)}} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{(S)}} \right) \quad (3)$$

where, $E_{1/2(W)}$ and $E_{1/2(S)}$ are the half-wave potentials in aqueous and aquoorganic mixtures, respec-

tively, and K is a constant. If the dielectric constant were the dominant factor, the shift in $E_{1/2(S)}$ would be a linear function $1/\epsilon_{(S)}$. The plots of $E_{1/2(S)}$ vs $1/\epsilon_{(S)}$ are linear (Fig. 3) which shows that the dielectric constant is indeed the dominant factor for the changes observed in the present study.

The addition of ethanol to water causes a destruction of the normal structure of water¹⁵ which influences the hydration layer surrounding the ions, leading to a shift of $E_{1/2}$ to less negative values. However, the shift of $E_{1/2}$ to more negative values observed in the present work may also be due to the absorption of the organic solvent molecules to some extent at the electrode surface. The accumulation of solvent molecules near the electrode surface retards the adsorption of the reducible species and also blocks the reactive centres on the electrode surface. Thus, the reduction process requires higher energy and hence the $E_{1/2}$ shifts to more negative potentials.

The kinetic parameters $k_{f,h}^0$ and the n_a values are given in Table 2. $k_{f,h}^0$ values are found to decrease with increase in the concentration of ethanol, which shows the increase in irreversibility. This is further supported by the decrease in n_a values with increase in the percentage of ethanol.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Prof. T. Navaneeth Rao, In-charge, Physical Chemistry Section and Prof. M. L. N. Reddy, Head, Department of Chemistry for their keen interest. One of the authors

(P. Y. S.) wishes to express his gratitude to U. G. C, New Delhi, for the award of a research fellowship.

References

1. P. C. TOMPKINS and C. L. A. SCHMIDT, *Univ. California, Pub. Physiol.*, 1944, **8**, 229.
2. H. H. G. JELLINEK and J. R. URWIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 168.
3. J. VOLKE and V. VOLKOVA, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1955, **20**, 1332.
4. H. LUND, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1963, **17**, 972.
5. C. TISSIER and AGOUTIN, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1973, **47**, 499.
6. L. CAMPANELLA, E. CHIACCHIERINI and M. PALCHETTI, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1972, **17**, 647.
7. O. R. BROWN, J. A. HARRISON and K. S. SASTRY, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1975, **58**, 387.
8. A. J. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry" 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1971, pp. 166, 169, 170.
9. J. E. LIND and R. M. FUOSS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 999.
10. K. ZUTSHI and B. MAHESHWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 813.
11. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", 4th. ed., Chapman & Hall, London, 1955, pp. 353, 365.
12. M. M. GHONEIM, Y. M. TEMERK and K. A. IDRIS, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16**, 300.
13. L. MEITES and Y. ISRAEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4903; L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", 2nd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1967, p. 145.
14. H. SADEK, R. M. ISSA and B. H. ABDET, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1971, **16**, 401.
15. M. M. GHONEIM, R. M. ISSA, I. M. ISSA and M. KHAT-TAB, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 19.
16. D. ILKOVIC and J. HEYROVSKY, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1955, **20**, 782.
17. A. EINSTEIN, *Ann. Phys.*, 1905, **15**, 549; 1906, **19**, 371; *Electrochem*, 1908, **14**, 235.
18. R. TAKAHASHI, *Talanta*, 1925, **12**, 122.